

Effect of nanocrystal shape on charge injection in CdSe/CdS dot-in-rod and rod-in-rod nano-heterostructures.

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ABSTRACT: Understanding of charge injection and transport in the arrays of colloidal nanocrystals (NCs) is important for development of many optoelectronic applications. Here, we present comparative spectroelectrochemical study of charge injection into thin NC films composed of spherical CdSe QDs, CdSe nanorods (NRs), and their corresponding dot-in-rod (DIR) and rod-in-rod (RIR) heterostructures. By simultaneously monitoring differential absorbance of the films at the CdSe core and CdS shell band-edge transitions, we resolve the potential-dependent and spatially distinct nature of the electron injection. The results show that charge injection is more efficient in DIR and RIR architectures than in spherical heterostructures, mainly due to the more open morphology, allowing for more efficient counterion diffusion. In asymmetric structures the charge injection is independent of the shell volume, as the injection mostly occurs through the thinnest part of the shell. The charge is injected first into the core and only after the core saturation, the charges are injected into the shell, with the transition potential governed by the core size and the shell geometry. These findings show that a shape of nano-heterostructures plays an important role in controlling the charge injection efficiency and location, with practical implications for NC-based optoelectronic devices.

■ INTRODUCTION

Size and shape-tunability of electronic properties colloidal semiconductor nanocrystals (NCs), enabled by quantum confinement effect, is one of their most fascinating characteristics from the fundamental as well as practical standpoint.¹ Development of approaches that enabled integration of two or more semiconductor materials within a single NC i.e., forming a core-shell nano-heterostructure, has further expanded the design space available for engineering of NCs with specific properties and functionalities.² As a result, colloidal nano-heterostructures have become attractive building blocks for the active layers of LEDs,³ lasers,⁴ photodetectors,⁵ photovoltaic cells⁶ and a wide range of other optoelectronic applications.⁷ In addition to favorable optical characteristics, the performance of NC-based optoelectronic devices also strongly depends on the efficiency with which charge carriers can be injected into or extracted from the nano-heterostructure and transported across arrays of NCs. Spectro-electrochemistry (SEC) has been shown to be a powerful tool for studying the charge injection and transport phenomena in such structures.⁸

Earlier spectro-electrochemical studies of thin films of spherical CdSe/CdS core-shell quantum dots have shown that electrochemical charge injection into this nano-heterostructure

strongly depends on the thickness of the CdS shell.⁹ Moderate CdS shell thickness progressively enhances injection efficiency, with the number of electrons injected into the core increasing from ~ 0.2 for bare CdSe to ~ 1.8 for an intermediate shell thickness of less than 10 CdS monolayers (ML). However, beyond a critical shell thickness of approximately 10 ML of CdS, the injection efficiency decreases, falling below ~ 0.8 electrons per NC. This result indicates that an excessively thick shell introduces a tunneling barrier that impedes carrier injection into the core.⁹ This counterintuitive behavior was systematically investigated by Ashokan et al.,¹⁰ who demonstrated that thicker CdS shells require progressively higher cathodic overpotentials for the electrons to tunnel through the CdS shell into the CdSe core. Furthermore, the charge injection process was found to be only quasi-reversible, as the electrons remain trapped in deep surface states, where they function as carrier recombination centers, causing incomplete PL recovery.¹⁰ While these studies established the central role of the shell in the charge injection into spherical core-shell nano-heterostructures, they offer limited insight about situations where the nano-heterostructures are non-spherical. Indeed, recent work on CdSe/CdS dot-in-rods and tetrapods has shown that NC shape can profoundly influence the interfacial charge transfer dynamics, with hole transfer rates differing by factor of 3–6 and

charge separated state lifetimes differing by over an order of magnitude between these two morphologies.¹¹

Motivated by these observations, in the present work we systematically examine how in anisotropic CdSe/CdS heterostructured NCs shape governs not only the efficiency but also the spatial location of the electrochemical charge injection. To this end, we performed comparative SEC studies on thin films prepared from spherical, zero-dimensional CdSe quantum dots and quasi-one-dimensional CdSe nanorods, as well as their corresponding dot-in-rod and rod-in-rod core-shell configurations, with comparable lateral particle dimensions. We demonstrate that nanocrystal shape has a pronounced effect on the charge injection onset potential, the overall charging efficiency, and the location of the injected charge within the heterostructure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CdSe QDs and CdSe/CdS dot in rod (DIR) were synthesized by the procedure described by Carbone et al.^{2c} CdSe NRs were synthesized by the procedure described by Peng et al.¹² and CdSe/CdS rod in rod (RIR) were synthesized by the modified procedure similar to Carbone et al.^{2c} Details of the synthesis procedures are described in the supplementary information (SI). TEM images and the size and shape analysis of the representative QDs, NRs, DIRs, and RIRs are shown in Fig. S1-S4 of the SI and summarized in Table 1. All the SEC measurements were performed in the thin film configuration. For thin film fabrication, the as-synthesized NCs were first washed with ethanol. The native bulky ligands (TOPO, TOP, ODPA, etc.) were exchanged with octylamine following the procedure of Manthiram et al.¹³ Details of the ligand exchange procedures are described in section 1.6 of the SI. Following successful ligand exchange, NC thin films were fabricated on ITO substrates via a layer-by-layer dip-coating method using 1,8-diaminooctane (DA) as a cross-linking ligand, as described in our previous work.¹⁴

Table 1. Summary of structural characteristics of the NC films studied in this work^a

Sample	$\langle d \rangle$ or $\langle w \rangle$ (nm)	$\langle l \rangle$ (nm)	AR	Native ligands	Subst. linkers
QD1	3.64±0.24	N/A	1	ODPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
DIR1	4.34±0.41	17.6±1.57	4.03	ODPA, HPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
DIR2	5.35±0.69	48.36±4.25	9.03	ODPA, HPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
NR1	3.75±0.51	14.42±2.38	3.84	TDPA, TOPO, TOP, TBP	DA
RIR1	5.29±0.78	41.76±3.45	7.89	ODPA, HPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
QD2	7.45±0.95	N/A	1	ODPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
DIR3	8.17±1.15	22.02±1.79	2.69	ODPA, HPA, TOPO, TOP	DA
NR2	5.55±0.52	20.52±2.18	3.69	TDPA, TOPO, TOP, TBP	DA
RIR2	6.83±1.04	126.47±18.98	18.51	ODPA, HPA, TOPO, TOP	DA

^a $\langle d \rangle$ = mean NC diameter, $\langle w \rangle$ = mean NC width, $\langle l \rangle$ = mean NC length and AR = aspect ratio.

Charge injection into small QD and DIR thin films. Fig. 1(a) - (i) shows results of the SEC studies of CdSe QD1, CdSe/CdS DIR1, and CdSe/CdS DIR2 thin films in the potential range E (V vs. Ag) = 0 to -1.6 V measured vs. Ag pseudo-reference electrode. Panels (a), (d), and (g) show contour maps of the change in the absorbance, $\Delta A = A_E - A_0$, for the QD1, DIR1, and DIR2 films, respectively, obtained as a difference in the absorbance at an applied potential, E , and at a zero applied potential (open circuit conditions). The contour map of the QD1 film is dominated by a ground state bleach at ~ 565 nm, consistent with band-edge state filling upon charge injection, accompanied by an induced absorption feature at wavelengths below 500 nm. The DIR1 thin film similarly exhibits a pronounced bleach centered at ~ 590 nm, reflecting a red-shift of the band edge transition relative to QD1, along with a secondary bleach feature at ~ 460 nm, consistent with band edge state filling of CdS shell and an induced absorption band below 450 nm. In contrast, the DIR2 thin film displays a markedly different spectral profile. The dominant bleach feature appears at ~ 460 nm, consistent with CdS band-edge state filling, while a comparatively weaker bleach is observed at ~ 597 nm for CdSe core (not fully visible). Additionally, induced absorption features are present below 450 nm.

Panels (b), (e), and (h) show the same results as shown in Panels (a), (d), and (g) of Fig. 1 but plotted as difference absorption spectra at various applied potentials. As in the contour plots, for QD1 film (panel (b)), the most dominant feature is the absorption bleach ($\Delta A < 0$) at ~ 565 nm. Similarly, for the DIR1 and DIR2 thin films (panels (e) and (h)), the most dominant bleach is observed at ~ 588 nm and ~ 465 nm, respectively, corresponding to prominent CdSe core bleach for DIR1 and CdS shell bleach for DIR2. In addition to these major features, the difference spectra show less pronounced bleach features, with peaks at ~ 460 nm for DIR1 and ~ 597 nm for DIR2 thin films. The bleach features in QD1 film, complemented by a sharp induced absorption ($\Delta A > 0$) feature with a peak at ~ 506 nm and a broad induced absorption feature below 475 nm. Similarly, in the DIR1 film, the induced absorption features are observed at ~ 525 nm and below 400 nm, and in the DIR2 film, the induced absorption features are observed at ~ 536 nm and below 400 nm. These enhanced absorbance observations in various core and core-shell NCs were attributed to Coulomb interactions between the electrochemically injected charge and the optically excited electron-hole pair.¹⁵ Such interactions can cause substantial shifts in transition energies and modify the selection rules governing the affected optical transitions, thereby giving rise to the induced absorption features observed in the corresponding spectral regions across the various core and core-shell NC samples.¹⁵

Panels (c), (f) and (i) in Fig. 1 show the changes in the absorption, plotted as a "relative absorbance bleach" ($\Delta A/A\%$) observed at the band edge transition of CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace) as a function of applied potential and the variation in the current detected over the same potential range (black trace) for the QD1, DIR1 and DIR2 films, respectively. As QD1 consists of a bare CdSe core with no CdS shell, the blue trace in panel (c) is included solely for direct comparison with the corresponding shell response observed in DIR1 and DIR2. In the case of QD1 (panel (c)), the relative absorption bleach begins at ca. -1.25 V, while current starts flowing earlier, at ca. -1.0 V. The gap between these two onset potentials, marked by

Figure 1. Contour plot of changes in the electronic absorption of the QD1 (a) DIR1 (d) and DIR2 (g) thin films with applied potential. Change in the absorbance of QD1 (b), DIR1 (e) and DIR2 (h) thin films with applied potential. Relative absorbance bleach of the core (red line) and shell (blue line) peak position with the applied potential for the QD1 (c), DIR1 (f) and DIR2 (i) thin films. The areas shaded with blue color indicate the potential range where the charge is injected primarily into the NC defect states and the areas shaded with red color indicates region, where the charge is injected primarily into the CdSe core or CdS shell. All experiments were performed at room temperature, using deaerated acetonitrile as a solvent and 0.1M TEAPF₆ as an electrolyte.

the blue-shaded region, corresponds to charge being injected into defect states, since such charges do not affect the band-edge absorption of the NCs¹⁴. This distinction arises because the measured current reflects the total charge transferred into the film regardless of where it resides, whereas the absorption bleach is sensitive only to electrons occupying the conduction band edge ($1S_e$) state, which blocks the corresponding optical transition. Consequently, the onset of current at ca. -1.0 V indicates that electrons are first trapped in sub-bandgap defect states, which lie energetically below the conduction band edge but do not contribute to the band edge bleach. Only when these trap states become populated does the additional driving force become sufficient to inject electrons into the $1S_e$ state, giving rise to the bleach observed beyond ca. -1.25 V. In contrast, the red shaded region indicates charge injection into the conduction band of the NC. As there is no CdS shell in QD1, no bleach is observed at ~ 460 nm. In the case of DIR1 film (panel (f)), the onset of CdSe core absorption bleach is observed at ca. -1.2 V and CdS shell absorption bleach is observed at ca. -1.25 V, while the initial current flow is detected at ca. -0.9 V. The small but measurable offset between the core and shell bleach onsets is consistent with the formation of a quasi-type-II

heterostructure, in which electrons and holes are partially delocalized across the core-shell interface. In contrast, the DIR2 film (panel (i)) exhibits a markedly earlier current onset at ca. -0.6 V, compared to bleach onsets of ca. -1.1 V (CdSe core) and ca. -1.2 V (CdS shell). The substantially wider blue-shaded region in DIR2 relative to QD1 and DIR1 points to a significantly larger population of sub-bandgap trap states. We attribute this to deep-level defect states arising from interfacial lattice mismatch at the core-shell interface, which becomes more pronounced in DIR2 due to its thicker CdS shell. These deep-level states, located well below the conduction band edge, are distinct from the shallow near band edge defects present in QD1 and DIR1.

Electrochemical electron injection into NC thin films requires charge balancing counter-ions from the electrolyte to diffuse through the NC thin film's porous network, and this ion transport represents the principal kinetic constraint for charge injection. In the QD1 film, comprising 3.64 nm CdSe QDs, the small NC size and correspondingly tight interparticle porosity severely restrict the diffusion of TEA⁺ counter-ions, limiting injection efficiency. As demonstrated in our previous work,¹⁴ in

films comprising QDs of this size, charge injection and transport are not efficient, resulting in an average of only ~ 0.3 electrons injected per QD at an applied potential of ca. -1.6 V see Fig S7 in SI. Details of calculating of the average number of injected electrons ($\langle N_{inj} \rangle$) is discussed in SI. Transitioning from the spherically symmetric QD1 to the asymmetric nanorod geometries of DIR1 and DIR2 substantially improves charge injection efficiency. DIR1 and DIR2 have nanorod widths of 4.34 nm and 5.35 nm and lengths of 17.6 nm and 48.36 nm, respectively. The anisotropic shape creates larger interparticle voids within the NC film, facilitating more effective counter ion diffusion and increase in electron injection yield. For DIR1, an average of ~ 0.68 electrons are injected into the CdSe core and ~ 0.1 electrons into the CdS shell at -1.6 V see Fig S7 in SI. Notably, despite its larger overall dimensions, DIR2 exhibits a comparable core injection yield (~ 0.61 electrons), but a markedly higher shell injection yield (~ 0.8 electrons) at the same applied potential (Fig S6 in SI).

Here we introduce an additional parameter, “differential (relative) bleach,” defined as $[(1/A_0) \cdot \Delta(A/A)]$. Plotting the differential relative bleach as a function of applied potential identifies the potential at which the majority of electron injection into the film takes place. As shown in Fig. S8 of the SI, for QD1, the bulk of electron injection occurs at ca. -1.44 V (vs. Ag), reflecting the restricted charge transport characteristic of this film. In the DIR1 film, the corresponding maxima occur at ca. -1.34 V and ca. -1.42 V (vs. Ag) for the CdSe core and CdS shell, respectively. For the DIR2 film, the majority of electron injection into the core occurs at ca. -1.26 V (vs. Ag), while shell injection peaks at ca. -1.42 V (vs. Ag). This trend indicates that core injection saturates first, followed by shell injection, with the

saturation point governed by the NC shape and size, as discussed in the following sections.

The observed SEC behavior is in sharp contrast with that reported for spherical CdSe/CdS core-shell QDs. Van der Stam et al.⁹ reported electron injection yields of 0.2, 1.8, and 0.9 electrons for bare CdSe cores (3.7 nm) and CdSe/CdS core-shell QDs with 6 monolayers (ML) (7.17 nm) and 10 ML (9.75 nm) of CdS shell, respectively. In spherical core-shell QDs, injected electrons must tunnel through the entire shell thickness to reach the core, such that increasing shell thickness progressively traps charge within the shell or at shell-related defect sites before it can reach the core. In contrast, in the CdSe/CdS DIR, charge is injected into the core by tunneling through the thinnest section of the shell, largely independent of the overall shell volume.

SEC of DIR2 provides evidence of the formation of pronounced deep-level defect states arising from interfacial lattice mismatch associated with the larger CdS shell, which act as charge traps that capture the injected carriers. Several observations support this interpretation. First, in the DIR2 film the measured current increases relative to QD1 and DIR1, mainly at lower potentials (blue shaded region). Yet this increase in charge injection produces very modest enhancement of the band-edge bleach, indicating that the majority of injected charges occupy trap states rather than the conduction band. Second, although charges confined to trap states do not directly alter the band edge transition probability, they strongly electrostatically interact with the optically excited band edge carriers, which manifests as a pronounced photoinduced absorption feature^{15a} observed during the reverse potential sweep from -1.6 V to 0 V in DIR2 in panel (i), which is not present in the panel (c) and (f).

Figure 2. (a, d) Contour maps showing the potential-dependent evolution of the electronic absorption spectra for the NR1 and RIR1 thin films, respectively. (b, e) Corresponding change in absorbance spectra of the NR1 and RIR1 films at selected applied potentials. (c, f) Relative absorbance bleach at the band-edge of the CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace) as a function of applied potential, for the NR1 and RIR1 films, respectively. The blue-shaded regions denote the potential range over which charge injection occurs predominantly into sub-bandgap defect states of the NCs, while the red-shaded regions mark the potential range associated with charge injection primarily into the band-edge states of the CdSe core or CdS shell.

Charge injection into small NR and RIR thin films. A striking contrast in charge injection observed between the CdSe/CdS DIR and CdSe/CdS core-shell QD geometries, motivated us to perform more systematic investigation of the underlying structural parameters. To disentangle the respective contributions of NC shape and core-shell heterostructure formation, we extended our study to CdSe NRs and their corresponding RIR architectures. Specifically, we synthesized CdSe NR1 with a width comparable to the diameter of QD1, with a mean length of $\langle l \rangle = 14.42$ nm and a mean width of $\langle w \rangle = 3.75$ nm. The corresponding rod-in-rod structure, RIR1, has dimensions of $\langle l \rangle = 41.76$ nm and $\langle w \rangle = 5.29$ nm.

Fig. 2(a) - (f) shows results of the SEC studies of CdSe NR1 and CdSe/CdS RIR1 thin films in the potential range E (V vs. Ag) = 0 to -1.6 V measured vs. Ag pseudo-reference electrode. Panels (a) and (d) show contour maps of the change in the absorbance, ΔA , for the NR1 and RIR1 films, respectively. The contour map of the NR1 film is dominated by a ground-state bleach at ~ 590 nm, consistent with band-edge state filling upon charge injection, accompanied by an induced absorption feature at wavelengths below 500 nm. The RIR1 thin film similarly exhibits a pronounced bleach centered at ~ 605 nm for the CdSe core, along with a secondary bleach feature at ~ 465 nm for CdS shell and an induced absorption band below 450 nm.

Panels (b) and (e) of Fig. 2 show the change in the absorbance at selected applied potentials for the NR1 and RIR1 films, respectively, complementing the information conveyed by the corresponding contour maps. For the NR1 film, two prominent ground-state bleach features are observed at ~ 590 nm and ~ 491 nm, consistent with a reduction in the optical transition probability of the $1\Sigma_g$ excitonic state of the CdSe NR1 upon electron injection. These bleach features are accompanied by a

photoinduced absorption band in the $\sim 500 - 550$ nm region, attributed to Coulomb interactions between the electrochemically injected charges and the optically excited electron-hole pair, as discussed previously.¹⁴ In contrast, the RIR1 film exhibits ground-state bleach features at ~ 605 nm and ~ 503 nm, consistent with band edge state filling upon charge injection into the CdSe core. Photoinduced absorption features are also observed at ~ 531 nm and below 450 nm, similarly attributed to Coulomb interactions between injected and optically excited carriers. Notably, an additional sharp bleach feature is observed at ~ 465 nm with an onset starting at approximately ca. -1.4 V (vs. Ag), consistent with band-edge state filling upon charge injection into the CdS shell. This confirms the sequential nature of electron injection into the two distinct semiconductor domains.

Panels (c) and (f) of Fig. 2 show the potential-dependent relative absorption bleach ($\Delta A/A\%$) monitored at the band edge of the CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace), together with the simultaneously recorded current (black trace), for the NR1 and RIR1 films, respectively. In both NR1 and RIR1, the onset of current flow attributable to charge injection into sub-bandgap defect states is observed at ca. -0.75 V (vs. Ag). Band-edge electron injection into the CdSe core starts at ca. -1.1 V for NR1 and at the notably lower potential of ca. -0.9 V for RIR1. As demonstrated in our previous work, narrow and short NRs impose a steric barrier to the diffusion of electrolyte counterions, limiting the efficiency of electrochemical charge injection and necessitating higher applied potentials (-1.1 V) to overcome this constraint compared to longer RIR1 (ca. -0.9 V). Moreover, on average, only ~ 0.67 electrons per NR are injected into NR1 thin film at -1.6 V see Fig S7 in SI. Nevertheless, this represents approximately twice the injection yield obtained for

Figure 3. (a, d) Potential-dependent contour maps of the electronic absorption spectra for the QD2 and DIR3 thin films, respectively. (b, e) Change of absorbance spectra of the QD2 and DIR3 films recorded at selected applied potentials. (c, f) Evolution of the band-edge relative absorbance bleach of the CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace) with applied potential, for the QD2 and DIR3 films, respectively. Potential ranges shaded in blue correspond to charge injection occurring predominantly into NC defect states, whereas regions shaded in red correspond to charge injection occurring predominantly into the band-edge states of the CdSe core

QD1, despite both samples sharing a comparable lateral dimension (NR1 width \approx QD1 diameter), demonstrating that the increased aspect ratio of NR1 significantly enhances charge injection efficiency. The RIR1 film exhibits a markedly higher injection yield, with ~ 1.75 electrons injected into the CdSe core and only ~ 0.04 electrons into the CdS shell (Fig S7 in SI).

As shown in Fig. S8 in the SI, the differential (relative) bleach of NR1 shows the majority of electron injection occurs at ca. -1.42 V (vs. Ag), reflecting the restricted charge transport characteristic of this narrow nanorod film. In contrast, for the RIR1 film, the majority of electron injection into the CdSe core occurs at a notably less negative potential of ca. -1.04 V (vs. Ag), while injection into the CdS shell peaks at ca. -1.48 V (vs. Ag). This significant shift in the core injection potential between NR1 and RIR1 is consistent with the trends discussed above, further confirming that the anisotropic core-shell geometry of RIR1 facilitates more efficient charge injection into the core relative to the bare nanorod. The dominant population of core states, together with the minimal shell contribution in RIR1, is consistent with our earlier observation for the DIR1 and DIR2 i.e., core injection saturates first, after which shell injection becomes the dominant pathway. Taken together, these results indicate that this sequential, core-first injection behavior is a general feature of elongated CdSe/CdS heterostructures, governed primarily by the core geometry rather than by the absolute shell volume.

Charge injection into big QD and DIR thin films. In this section, we extend our investigation to a larger CdSe core size, increasing the QD diameter from 3.5 nm to 6.2 nm (QD2), in order to examine the effect of spherical core size on charge injection. The corresponding CdSe/CdS dot-in-rod nanocrystals (DIR3) were synthesized using this larger 7.45 nm core, with a mean rod length of $\langle l \rangle = 21.9$ nm and a mean rod width of $\langle w \rangle = 8.1$

nm. Fig. 3(a)–(f) presents the SEC studies of the CdSe QD2 and CdSe/CdS DIR3 thin films over the potential range E (V vs. Ag) = 0 to -1.6 V, measured against an Ag reference electrode. Panels (a) and (d) display the contour maps of the differential absorbance, ΔA , for the QD2 and DIR3 films, respectively. The QD2 contour map is dominated by a ground-state bleach at ~ 635 nm, consistent with $1S_e$ state filling upon charge injection, accompanied by an induced absorption feature below 500 nm arising from electrostatic interactions between the charges. The DIR3 contour map exhibits a pronounced bleach centered at ~ 640 nm, corresponding to band-edge state filling of the CdSe core, along with a secondary bleach feature at ~ 475 nm attributed to electron injection into the CdS shell, and an induced absorption band below 450 nm consistent with Coulomb interactions, as discussed previously. Panels (b) and (e) of Fig. 3 show the corresponding ΔA spectra at selected applied potentials. For QD2 (panel (b)), the dominant ground-state bleach ($\Delta A < 0$) appears at ~ 635 nm, accompanied by a less pronounced bleach at ~ 530 nm; both features reflect charge injection into the $1S_e$ state of the QDs. In the DIR3 film, prominent bleach features are observed at ~ 640 nm, ~ 530 nm, and ~ 475 nm. The bleach features at 640 nm and 530 nm are attributed to charge injection into the CdSe core, while the feature at 475 nm corresponds to charge injection into the CdS shell.

Panels (c) and (f) of Fig. 3 present the potential-dependent relative differential bleach ($\Delta A/A\%$) recorded at the bleach maxima of the CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace), alongside the corresponding current trace (black), for the QD2 and DIR3 films, respectively. In both films, the current associated with charge injection into sub-bandgap defect states sets in within the blue-shaded region, at ca. -0.75 V for QD2 and ca. -0.6 V for DIR3. Band-edge electron injection into the CdSe core follows shortly after, with an onset of ca. -0.9 V for QD2 and a

Figure 4. (a, d) Potential-dependent contour maps of the electronic absorption spectra for the NR1 and RIR2 thin films, respectively. (b, e) Change of absorbance spectra of the NR1 and RIR2 films recorded at selected applied potentials. (c, f) Evolution of the band-edge differential absorbance at the bleach maxima of the CdSe core (red trace) and CdS shell (blue trace) with applied potential, for the NR2 and RIR2 films, respectively. Potential ranges shaded in blue correspond to charge injection occurring predominantly into NC defect states, whereas regions shaded in red correspond to charge injection occurring predominantly into the band-edge states of the CdSe core or CdS shell.

comparatively lower ca. -0.8 V for DIR3. This pattern mirrors what we observed for the NR1/RIR1 pair, reinforcing the conclusion that larger NCs facilitate easier charge injection than their smaller counterparts, owing to the more favorable diffusion of electrolyte counter-ions within the less constrained film morphology.

Differential relative bleach analysis was also performed for the QD2 and DIR3 thin films. As shown in Fig. S10 in the SI, for QD2, the majority of electron injection occurs at ca. -1.3 V (vs. Ag). For the DIR3 film, the majority of electron injection into the CdSe core occurs at a notably less negative potential of ca. -1.05 V (vs. Ag), while injection into the CdS shell peaks at ca. -1.24 V (vs. Ag). This shift in the core injection potential between QD1 and QD2 shows that charge injection is easy and efficient in big QDs and on the other side QD2 and DIR3 mirrors the trend observed for the smaller QD/DIR and NR/RIR pairs, further confirming that the asymmetric core-shell geometry facilitates more efficient charge injection into the core relative to the bare spherical core, regardless of the absolute core size.

Charge injection into big NR and RIR thin films. In this section, we have extended our spectroelectrochemical investigation to a larger CdSe NR2 ($\langle l \rangle = 20.52$ nm and $\langle w \rangle = 5.55$ nm) along with its core-shell RIR2 ($\langle l \rangle = 126.47$ nm and $\langle w \rangle = 6.83$ nm) thin films. Fig. 4(a) - (f) shows results of the SEC studies of CdSe NR2 and CdSe/CdS RIR2 thin films in the potential range E (V vs. Ag) = 0 to -1.6 V measured vs. Ag reference electrode. The contour map of the panel (a) and (d) shows the change in the absorbance, ΔA , for the NR2 and RIR2 films, respectively. The results shown in contour maps show that ground state bleach of the NR2 is located at ~ 637 nm and ~ 525 nm, along with an induced absorption feature below 500 nm. However, RIR2 thin film similarly exhibits a pronounced bleach centered at ~ 642 nm and ~ 527 nm, which is ground state bleach of the CdSe core in RIR2 thin film, along with an induced absorption band below 450 nm.

Panels (b) and (e) of Fig. 4 provide complementary information to the contour maps, presenting the differential absorbance spectra of the NR2 and RIR2 films at selected applied potentials. Consistent with the trends established above, the NR2 film displays two principal bleach features, at ~ 637 nm and ~ 525 nm, both arising from charge accumulation in the $1\Sigma_g$ state of the nanorod. The RIR2 film shows analogous bleach features, slightly red-shifted to ~ 642 nm and ~ 527 nm, a shift attributable to the small conduction-band offset between CdSe and CdS that permits partial electron delocalization into the shell. The close correspondence between the RIR2 and NR2 spectral signatures indicates that the majority of injected charge remains localized within the CdSe core of the RIR2 heterostructure. A weak additional bleach feature, assigned to the CdS shell, emerges at ~ 475 nm only at the most negative potential investigated (-1.6 V).

Panels (c) and (f) of Fig. 4 present the corresponding potential-dependent relative bleach ($\Delta A/A\%$) at the core (red) and shell (blue) bleach maxima, together with the measured current (black trace), for the NR2 and RIR2 films. In both films, current associated with sub-bandgap defect-state filling appears within the blue-shaded region beginning at ca. -0.6 V. Band-edge electron injection into the CdSe core itself begins later, at ca. -0.9 V for both NR2 and RIR 2. By -1.6 V, an average of ~ 1.71 electrons have been injected into the NR2 film (Fig. S6), with the bulk of this injection occurring around ca. -1.1 V (Fig. S11). The RIR2

film accommodates a somewhat lower average of ~ 1.12 electrons in the CdSe core over the same potential range (Fig. S6), with the dominant injection potential similarly centered at ca. -1.12 V (Fig. S11). This reversal where the bare nanorod outperforms its core-shell counterpart in core injection yield is analogous to the behavior observed in the DIR2 series, where an excessively thick CdS shell was shown to redirect a significant fraction of injected charge away from the core. Consistent with this interpretation, the RIR2 film, which possesses the longest rod length and largest total volume among all core-shell architectures examined in this study, exhibits shell charging, with ~ 0.22 electrons injected at ca. -1.6 V. As discussed in the context of DIR2, this behavior is attributed to the presence of pronounced deep-level interfacial defect states arising from lattice mismatch at the core-shell boundary, which becomes increasingly significant as shell volume grows, trapping a substantial fraction of injected charges before they can reach the CdSe core and rendering their contribution invisible in the band-edge bleach signal.

■ CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that nanocrystal shape and core-shell geometry, beyond core size and shell thickness alone, play a major role in the thermodynamics and efficiency of electrochemical charge injection in colloidal CdSe/CdS thin films. Across spherical QDs (QD1, QD2), nanorods (NR1, NR2), and their corresponding dot-in-rod (DIR1-3) and rod-in-rod (RIR1, RIR2) heterostructures, transitioning to anisotropic geometries leads consistently to enhanced injection efficiencies, attributed primarily to improved electrolyte counter-ion diffusion within more porous morphology of nanorod-based films. In all DIR and RIR architectures, charge injection followed a sequential, core-first mechanism, with core filling saturating before shell injection became significant. This is in stark contrast to spherical core-shell QDs, where the electrons must tunnel through the entire width of the shell, making injection efficiency strongly shell-thickness dependent. In anisotropic heterostructures, charge instead tunnels through the thinnest section of the shell, regardless of the total shell volume. These findings establish nanocrystal shape as a useful design parameter for controlling charge injection efficiency, onset potential, and spatial charge location, with direct implications for engineering NC-based optoelectronic devices.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://>

Details of QDs, NRs, DIRs and RIRs syntheses, thin film fabrication, absorption and emission spectra suspensions in hexanes, additional results of charge injection and charge transfer studies.

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M.R. Conceptualization, funding acquisition, materials syntheses, thin film fabrication, characterization, data analysis, visualization, co-wrote the original manuscript. E.R.A performed material thin film fabrication materials characterization. I.T and V.V performed materials characterization. M.S. Conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, data analysis, visualization, co-wrote the original manuscript. All authors contributed to the editing of the manuscript.

Notes

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